

REVIEW OF QUASI-PHASEMATCHING AND PERIODICALLY POLED LITHIUM NIOBATE

Lawrence E. Myers

*USAF Wright Laboratory, EO Laser Applications Branch
WLA/JL, 2700 D Street, Suite 2, WPAFB, OH 45433-7405*

ABSTRACT: The technique of quasi-phasematching allows tailoring the properties of existing well-developed nonlinear optical materials for the desired interaction. Practical implementation of quasi-phasematching is now possible with the recent development of periodically poled lithium niobate (PPLN). This paper describes the status and use of engineered nonlinear optical materials, particularly PPLN, and their impact on quasi-phasematched nonlinear optical devices. Recent successes with these materials include high-power optical parametric oscillators widely tunable over the technologically important mid-infrared spectral range 1-5 μm . This technology is useful for a variety of military, scientific, and commercial applications.

1. INTRODUCTION

Nonlinear optical frequency conversion is useful for generating coherent radiation where convenient laser sources are unavailable.[1] Laser sources are either limited to discrete lines or relatively narrow spectral regions. Many applications require wavelengths where direct laser sources do not operate, or where existing lasers are inefficient, complex, or otherwise impractical for many uses. Starting with well-developed lasers, particularly solid-state and diode lasers in the near-IR, coherent light in the mid-IR, visible, and UV spectral regions can be generated by frequency conversion in a suitable nonlinear optical material. Air Force applications that rely on nonlinear optical frequency conversion include displays, laser radar, remote sensing, IR countermeasures, and spectroscopic instrumentation.

The utility of nonlinear optics has been and still is predominantly limited by the availability of suitable nonlinear optical materials.[2] Suitability of a material requires the simultaneous satisfaction of a number of conditions, including a significantly large nonlinearity, transparency at the operating wavelengths, damage resistance, and availability of high-quality crystals with dimensions of at least 1 cm. Beyond the basic properties, the condition that eliminates most potential materials from application is the requirement of phasematching. However, the technique of quasi-phasematching allows engineering the material properties to match the phasematching requirements of any desired interaction. While quasi-phasematching was invented

shortly after the first nonlinear optical experiment,[3] it has not been of great importance because of the lack of practical processing methods for fabricating materials with the micron-scale structures required for its implementation. Recent advances in the fabrication of periodically poled ferroelectric materials has dramatically changed this situation, such that practical quasi-phasematched devices are currently being demonstrated at a rapid rate.[4]

The focus of this paper is the development of the material periodically poled lithium niobate (PPLN) and its application to quasi-phasematched (QPM) optical parametric oscillators (OPOs) operating in the mid-IR from 1-5 μm . In Section 2, background on quasi-phasematched nonlinear optics is presented. Section 3 briefly describes the processing methods for fabricating PPLN material. Section 4 reviews the OPOs that have been demonstrated using this material. In Section 5, directions for future research will be discussed.

2. QUASI-PHASEMATCHED NONLINEAR OPTICS

Optical radiation propagating within a nonlinear optical material can result in the generation of radiation at other frequencies. Interaction through the nonlinear polarization of the medium gives rise to frequency components at the second harmonic, sum frequency, and difference frequency of the input waves. The coupling of the input waves to the nonlinear polarization is described through the nonlinear susceptibility \mathbf{d} . For the example of parametric generation, in which a pump wave at ω_3 generates waves at the signal ω_2 and idler ω_1 , the nonlinear polarization at frequency ω_2 is $\mathbf{P}_{\omega_2} = \epsilon_0 \mathbf{d} \mathbf{E}_{\omega_3} \mathbf{E}_{\omega_1}^*$ where \mathbf{E}_{ω_1} and \mathbf{E}_{ω_3} are the complex field amplitudes of the idler and pump waves, ϵ_0 is the vacuum permittivity, and the factor of 2 results from the commonly used definition of \mathbf{d} . This nonlinear polarization acts as a source to generate the signal field \mathbf{E}_{ω_2} . The value of \mathbf{d} is a material-specific parameter that depends on the polarization of the interacting waves in the given interaction.

In a general three-wave interaction, the frequencies ω_1 , ω_2 , and ω_3 must satisfy the energy conservation criterion $\omega_1 + \omega_2 = \omega_3$. The phase of the fields is also important because the phase relationship determines the direction of power flow between the interacting waves. Dispersion in the material results in frequency-dependent phase velocities, leading to a varying phase relationship. The phase variation per unit length is described by the phase velocity mismatch

Fig. 1. Growth of generated wave for phasematched, not phasematched, and quasi-phasematched (QPM) interactions.

$\Delta k = k_3 - k_2 - k_1$ where $k_j = \omega_j n_j / c$ ($j = 1, 2, 3$) is the wave vector of the corresponding wave with refractive index n_j . As shown in Fig. 1, when $\Delta k \neq 0$, the phase changes as the waves propagate through the crystal so the power oscillates between them and there is no efficient generation. The coherence length is the distance where the accumulated phase mismatch is π and the power flow reverses direction.

When the interaction is phasematched ($\Delta k = 0$), power is efficiently transferred to the generated field as the waves propagate through the crystal. Phasematching is typically achieved by using the birefringence of the material (i.e. the polarization dependence of the refractive indices) to offset the dispersion. The refractive indices of a crystal can be changed to some extent by temperature and by the angle between the propagation direction and the crystal axis. However, there are only limited instances of a fortuitous combination of material properties that allow phasematching for most interactions of interest. An important example of an available phasematched process is second harmonic generation of 1.064- μm lasers using angle-tuned KTP.

In a quasi-phasematched interaction, the sign of the nonlinear susceptibility is reversed every coherence length so that the phase of the interaction is reset and efficient generation is also obtained.[5] Shifting the phasematching peak in the temporal frequency domain in a quasi-phasematched device is analogous to beam steering in a phased array antenna in which the spatial frequency of the radiation is shifted by phase resets within the aperture. Thus the main advantage of quasi-phasematching is that efficient generation can be achieved independent of the inherent material properties by fabricating a periodically reversed structure in the nonlinear susceptibility.

For quasi-phasematched OPOs, most of the conventional OPO theory can be applied with redefinitions of the effective nonlinear coefficient and the wave vector mismatch.[6] The nonlinear coefficient for quasi-phasematching is $d_Q = (2/\pi)d_{\text{eff}}$ where d_{eff} is the nonlinear coefficient for the

same conventionally phasematched process and the factor of $2/\pi$ comes from the first Fourier component of the modulated structure of the nonlinear susceptibility (a square wave as shown in Fig. 1). The wave vector mismatch for quasi-phasematching is $\Delta k_Q = k_3 - k_2 - k_1 - K_g$ where the grating vector is $K_g = 2\pi/\Lambda$ for grating period Λ analogous to the wave vectors. These substitutions result in several distinct advantages for QPM OPOs. The nonlinear coefficient for a QPM process is reduced by the factor of $2/\pi$ when comparing the same processes. However, a QPM process can make use of nonlinear coefficients that are inaccessible to conventional birefringently phasematched processes. In particular for the case of lithium niobate, the only birefringently phasematched OPO interaction requires extraordinary polarization (i.e. polarization parallel to the crystal axis) for the pump wave and ordinary polarization (i.e. polarization perpendicular to the crystal axis) for the signal and idler using the d_{31} element of the nonlinear susceptibility tensor. However, a QPM OPO can operate with all waves having extraordinary polarization using the d_{33} component. Because d_{33} is approximately 7 times larger than d_{31} and it enters the OPO gain equation as d^2 , the nonlinear drive of a QPM OPO is >20 times larger than that of the conventional OPO, even including the $2/\pi$ reduction factor.

The substitution for the wave vector mismatch results in another important advantage for QPM OPOs. The inclusion of the grating vector gives the OPO designer an adjustment mechanism that is not dependent on intrinsic material properties. Thus tuning can be accomplished by adjusting temperature and angle as in a conventional OPO, but also by adjusting the grating period. An example of this is presented in Section 4.2. Phasematching can also be designed to be noncritical (i.e. no first-order dependence on angle of incidence) at any desired temperature for any wavelength within the transparency range of the material. The advantage of noncritical phasematching is that there is no angular walk-off of the interacting waves and the angular acceptance is large, giving greater efficiency. Noncritical phasematching is possible in conventional OPOs only at a few fortuitous operating points; QPM OPOs can be designed for noncritical phasematching at any operating point. Control of phasematching through design of the grating vector also permits extending the range of operation of existing nonlinear materials and using materials that do not have enough birefringence for conventional birefringent phasematching. In addition, novel designs are possible, such as tailoring the spectral properties of the phasematching function and combining multiple nonlinear processes into a single device.

3. PERIODICALLY POLED LITHIUM NIOBATE

Implementation of quasi-phasematching requires a processing technique to create micron-scale periodic modulation of the nonlinear susceptibility. Ferroelectrics are a common class of useful nonlinear optical materials. Reversal of the polarity of the spontaneous ferroelectric

polarization (i.e. the built-in dipole moment) of the crystal results in reversal of the sign of the nonlinear susceptibility. Thus quasi-phasematching can be implemented by building into these materials a grating of ferroelectric domains with their polarities periodically reversed, which is referred to as periodic poling. A variety of techniques have been employed to effect periodic poling, including chemical indiffusion and modulation of control parameters during crystal growth. Progress has accelerated in the past few years with the introduction of the method of applying an external electric field using lithographically patterned electrodes. Periodic poling of the ferroelectrics KTP, RTA, and lithium tantalate has been demonstrated, but the most development has occurred with lithium niobate.

The processing of periodically poled lithium niobate (PPLN) used in the devices described in Section 4 has been reported in detail elsewhere.[6] The process consists basically of two steps: lithographic fabrication of an electrode structure on the surface of a lithium niobate wafer, and application of an electric field to reverse the domain orientation. The substrate material is standard commercial optical-grade lithium niobate wafers. The electrode consists of regions of conducting material which contact the surface where domain reversal is desired, and insulating material which contact the surface where domain reversal is not wanted. This electrode is fabricated using materials and techniques common in the microelectronics industry. The sample is placed into a circuit containing a high-voltage pulser. The required field strength for domain reversal is 21 kV/mm. A liquid electrode fixture has been found to be useful for connecting the sample to the circuit and avoiding dielectric breakdown problems due to the high fields involved. The poling process can be controlled by monitoring the charge that is transferred through the circuit to compensate the new domain polarity.

Electric-field poling is a one-time permanent process. After domain reversal has been accomplished, the field can be turned off, the electrode removed, and the crystal handled, polished, and coated like standard lithium niobate. We have

Fig. 2. Cross-section view of a 0.5-mm thick PPLN crystal with 15.5- μm period.

seen that domains show no evidence of degradation over several years and they are stable at temperatures up to 850 °C. A sample of a piece of PPLN is shown Fig. 2. Comparing with Fig. 1, the domain structure has nearly the ideal characteristics for quasi-phasematching. The piece shown has a 15- μm grating period. Periods as short as 10 μm have been fabricated with this basic process. Shorter periods have also been demonstrated using similar methods.[7, 8] For the IR OPO devices described in the next section, the required domain periods for $\Delta k = 0$ are $\sim 30 \mu\text{m}$ which is readily attainable. Current state of the art for IR devices permits processing of full 3-inch-diameter, 0.5-mm-thick wafers yielding crystals $>60\text{-mm}$ long. Research is underway to extend this to 1-mm-thick wafer substrates.

4. QUASI-PHASEMATCHED OPTICAL PARAMETRIC OSCILLATORS

The first device-quality 0.5-mm-thick PPLN crystals suitable for use in OPO experiments were obtained in Feb 1994. The rapid development of material processing and the availability of increasingly longer PPLN crystals over the following two years have led to a variety of OPO demonstrations. These devices are summarized in this section.

4.1 First QPM OPO in a Bulk Nonlinear Optical Material

In the summer of 1994, we demonstrated the first QPM OPO in a bulk nonlinear optical material using a 5-mm-long, 0.5-mm-thick PPLN crystal with 31- μm period.[9] The device was pumped by a 1.064- μm Nd:YAG Q-switched laser with 7-ns pulses at 100 Hz. The cavity was a simple, linear resonator as shown in Fig. 3. We measured a threshold of 0.145 mJ for a single-passed pump and 0.080 mJ for a double-passed pump. We tuned this device from 1.66-2.128- μm signal and 2.95-2.128- μm idler by adjusting the temperature from 25-180 °C. A key result of this experiment was that the damage threshold of the material was unchanged by the poling process. By raising the pump energy to

Fig. 3. Typical experimental set-up for QPM OPOs.

intentionally damage the crystals, we measured a damage threshold of 3 J/cm^2 which agrees with the previous reports for single-domain lithium niobate.

Another important result of this experiment was that there was no loss at the domain boundary walls, since our measured threshold matched the theoretically predicted value. To further investigate the loss in the material, we placed PPLN crystals in an optical resonator with a bare-cavity finesse of 200, pumped by a single-frequency cw Tm:YAG laser at $2.014 \mu\text{m}$. [6] The losses of the PPLN could be determined from the reduction in cavity finesse manifested by the sharpness of the interferometric transmission peaks of the $2\text{-}\mu\text{m}$ laser through the resonator. We measured PPLN samples with AR-coated surfaces which had 0.3% per surface loss. We were able to measure no additional loss above that attributable to the coatings. Since the number of domain boundary walls in these pieces ranged from 600-1000 (9-15-mm long), even a small amount of added loss at each boundary wall would have been detected. Therefore, the poling process adds no loss over that of single-domain lithium niobate.

4.2 Multi-grating QPM OPO

The control of phasematching through the grating vector enables novel device designs. We fabricated a widely tunable QPM OPO with multiple gratings on a single PPLN chip. [10] As shown in Fig. 4, the PPLN chip has individual grating regions $500\text{-}\mu\text{m}$ wide and separated by $50 \mu\text{m}$. The grating periods ranged from $26\text{-}32 \mu\text{m}$ in $0.25\text{-}\mu\text{m}$ steps. The crystals used for this experiment were 26-mm long. The

Fig. 4. Top view of a portion of the multi-grating PPLN chip. The left panel shows sections with grating periods from $29\text{-}30.5 \mu\text{m}$; the right panel shows a close-up of the $29\text{-}\mu\text{m}$ grating section.

experimental set-up was similar to that shown in Fig. 3. The pump laser was a cw-diode-pumped acousto-optically Q-switched Nd:YAG laser at $1.064 \mu\text{m}$ with 7-ns FWHM pulse length at 1 kHz. The cavity mode was confocally focused in the crystal (i.e. $L/b=1$ where L is the crystal length and $b = 2\pi m w_0^2 / \lambda$ is the confocal parameter for beam waist w_0 and wavelength λ), and the pump beam was matched to the cavity mode. The mirrors were coated for singly resonant operation at the $1.54\text{-}\mu\text{m}$ signal and the output coupler was 90% reflective. The crystal surfaces were not coated so they contributed 14 % per surface loss. The measured threshold for this device was 0.006 mJ .

The OPO was tuned by translating the crystal through the resonator so that the pump beam interacted with the different grating periods as shown in Fig. 5. We demonstrated output tunable from $1.36\text{-}4.83 \mu\text{m}$ as shown in Fig. 6. Intermediate wavelengths can be obtained by making finer grating increments, or continuous tuning is available with temperature adjustment or by making a fanned grating

Fig. 5. The multi-grating OPO is tuned by translating the PPLN crystal through the OPO resonator so the pump interacts with different grating periods.

Fig. 6. Wavelength tuning with the multi-grating PPLN OPO. The dashed curves are calculations using dispersion formulas at $25 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ and $200 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$; the circles are measured data points at $25 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$.

instead of discrete steps. We were initially surprised at being able to operate this OPO out to as far as 4.83 μm since lithium niobate is not commonly considered to be a useful material beyond 4.3 μm . Examination of the absorption coefficient showed that it is polarization dependent such that the extraordinary index has lower absorption than the ordinary index. Since the extraordinary polarization is used for the idler in a QPM OPO with d_{33} , but in a conventional birefringently phase-matched OPO the idler must use ordinary polarization, QPM OPOs in PPLN have better operation beyond 4 μm than would be expected based on previous research. In fact, the transmission of the extraordinary index of lithium niobate in the 4-5- μm range actually appears to be better than that of KTA which is typically used for OPOs in this region.

The key result of this experiment was that the level of control of the ferroelectric domain structure now possible permits novel devices to be realized. Our multi-grating QPM OPO is one example. It allows non-critically phase-matched operation over the entire mid-IR transparency range of lithium niobate with a single crystal. The 26-mm-long PPLN crystals used in this experiment gave thresholds as low as 0.006 mJ, yet even at these low pump energies PPLN OPOs run robustly (typically 70% pump depletion at 8 times threshold). With the better IR transmission accessible through quasi-phase-matching, these devices promise to be useful sources of widely tunable coherent radiation in the mid-IR.

4.3 High-power, High-repetition-rate PPLN OPOs

The high gain and low loss of PPLN are especially useful with cw-diode-pumped acousto-optically Q-switched solid-state lasers. These lasers can run at pulse repetition rates up to 50 kHz, and a variety of commercial products are available. However, with cw diode pumping, the available pulse energy of these lasers is low, and high-repetition-rate operation produces longer pulses and hence lower peak powers. Even with these low-peak-power pulses, PPLN OPOs can run efficiently.

We demonstrated high-repetition-rate pumping with a commercial cw-diode-pumped Q-switched Nd:YAG laser at 1.064 μm (Lightwave Model 210S).[11] This laser can run from 0-50 kHz. The pulse length is 22 ns, 40 ns, and 63 ns at 1 kHz, 10 kHz, and 20 kHz respectively. Above 10 kHz, the average power limits at 5.8 W; below 1 kHz, the maximum pulse energy is 1.5 mJ. The PPLN crystal was 15-mm long and had AR coated end faces for the 1.54- μm signal. We used an experimental set-up similar to that shown in Fig. 3. The output coupler had 60% signal reflectivity. The PPLN crystal was heated to 70 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ to prevent photorefractive effects which add loss.

We obtained oscillation at repetition rates as high as 32 kHz. Pumping at 10 kHz with 5.8 W, we generated 2 W at 1.54- μm signal and 0.6 W at 3.45- μm idler. We saw no saturation effects in the output power, indicating that thermal

loading is not an issue up to the pump power levels used in this experiment. Thus the average power of PPLN OPOs can be increased by taking advantage of high-repetition-rate solid-state pump lasers. Operation at elevated temperature, necessary to prevent photorefractive effects at high average power, is not a problem since the QPM period can be designed for operation at any desired temperature.

4.4 CW Doubly Resonant OPO with Direct Diode Laser Pumping

The advantage of PPLN for pumping with low-peak-power lasers is especially apparent in the limiting case of cw pump lasers. An OPO directly pumped by a cw diode laser would be a particularly compact and efficient implementation. However, direct diode pumping is difficult with conventional materials because of power and wavelength requirements imposed by birefringent phase-matching. With the engineerable phase-matching and high gain of PPLN, we demonstrated the first OPO directly pumped by a commercial cw diode laser.[12]

The experimental set-up was again similar to that shown in Fig. 3, with the substitution of a master-oscillator/power-amplifier diode laser (SDL MOPA Model 5762) for the pump. This laser produced 500 mW at 977.6 nm with linewidth ~ 25 MHz. To prevent feedback into the laser, -60 dB of isolation was required. In the OPO linear cavity, round-trip power losses for the resonant waves were $\sim 2\%$. The measured threshold was as low as 61 mW and the output power as high as 64 mW with 370 mW pump. This device operated near degeneracy at 1.96 μm . Tuning from 1.85-2.08 μm was observed by moving the cavity mirror with a piezoelectric transducer.

While this device is impressive for operating directly with a diode laser pump, the requirement to simultaneously satisfy the double resonance condition introduces instabilities. The device is susceptible to mode hops with small perturbations of cavity length or temperature. This is not unique to this device but is a problem for all doubly resonant OPOs. Attempts to improve their stability have met with limited success even with complex control loops and cavity designs. One improvement is to fabricate the resonator mirrors directly on the PPLN crystal so that the monolithic structure is less susceptible to cavity length variation. We have in fact built such a monolithic PPLN OPO, but there are still remaining stabilization difficulties.[13] The singly resonant OPO described in the next section avoids the double resonance stability problems.

4.5 CW Singly Resonant PPLN OPOs

A singly resonant OPO does not have the stability problems of the double resonance, but its threshold is 2 orders of magnitude higher than the doubly resonant OPO. Hence most singly resonant OPOs are pumped by pulsed lasers to make use of the high gain available with high-peak-

power pulses. The first cw singly resonant OPO was demonstrated in 1992 with KTP pumped by a custom-built resonantly doubled single-frequency Nd:YAG laser. This device operated near degeneracy and was not tunable so its utility was limited, but it did show the important result of stable operation in a cw singly resonant OPO.

We recently demonstrated a practical implementation of cw singly resonant OPOs using PPLN.[14, 15] The pump laser was a prototype 17-W version of Lightwave's Model 220 cw-diode-pumped 1.064- μm Nd:YAG laser. The laser had single spatial mode, but multiple longitudinal modes (~ 9 modes, 2.2-GHz linewidth). The PPLN crystal was 50-mm long with 29.75- μm period for first-order quasi-phaseshmatching at 1.57- μm signal and 3.3- μm idler at 175 $^{\circ}\text{C}$. Both linear and ring cavities were used. The threshold was as low as 2.6 W, and it generated as much as 3.3 W at 3.3 μm . Pump depletion was as high as 93 %, and ~ 80 % of quantum-limited performance was obtained in extracted idler power. The resonant signal wave was low noise (1% rms) and ran on a single longitudinal mode (linewidth $< 0.02 \text{ cm}^{-1}$) in spite of the multi-mode pump laser. Using a multi-grating PPLN chip similar to that described in Section 4.2, we demonstrated > 1 W output over the idler tuning range 3.3-3.9 μm .

5. FUTURE RESEARCH DIRECTIONS

In the area of material processing, there is still research work to be done in fabricating PPLN with the short periods needed for visible interactions. Green light from second harmonic generation of Nd:YAG lasers requires 6.8- μm periods, and blue light from second harmonic generation of diode lasers requires ~ 4 - μm periods. The high conversion efficiency in a QPM device makes these attractive approaches for generation of visible light for display applications.

For IR OPOs, there is a need to fabricate material on thicker substrates in order to increase the aperture size and the energy handling capability. IR devices 0.5-mm thick are currently readily fabricated, and some research results have been obtained with 1-mm thick substrates.[16] It is possible to imagine that 2-mm thick pieces might be possible.

Other ferroelectric materials are also of interest. Lithium tantalate, KTP, and most recently RTA have been periodically poled.[17-19] These materials have advantages over PPLN in some properties; however, the state of development of the substrate crystals is not nearly as mature as that of lithium niobate. Thus more research must be done to make these crystals viable practical alternatives. There is an on-going search to identify other ferroelectrics, particularly those transmitting in the UV and beyond 4 μm , which might lend themselves to the electric-field poling process. Diffusion-bonded semiconductors are another type of quasi-phaseshmatched material which is especially interesting for high-power generation in the mid- to far-IR.

In the area of devices, there will be an increasing variety of sources which are now possible for the first time with these new materials for quasi-phaseshmatching. The ability to

pattern the domain structure using a lithographic mask permits novel device designs. The widely tunable multi-grating OPO described in Section 4.2 is one example. Others include modified tuning bandwidths, multiple frequency outputs, and combinations of nonlinear processes in a single device (e.g. sum- or difference-frequency generation from OPO outputs).

PPLN is currently having the most significant impact on devices using low-peak-power pump lasers. Thus direct diode pumping and pumping with high-repetition-rate cw-diode-pumped solid-state lasers are useful approaches to potential commercial devices. The practical cw singly resonant OPO represents a breakthrough in generation of stable, coherent high-power output in the mid-IR. QPM OPOs using PPLN may potentially have significant impact on Air Force and commercial applications.

ACKNOWLEDGMENTS

This work was made possible with the support of the USAF Wright Laboratory, Wright-Patterson AFB OH, and the Center for Nonlinear Optical Materials at Stanford University. I wish to thank Walt Bosenberg of Lightwave Electronics for collaboration on most of the device demonstrations described here.

REFERENCES

1. For background on nonlinear optics, see R. W. Boyd, *Nonlinear Optics* (Academic, San Diego, 1992) or A. Yariv, *Quantum Electronics*, 3rd edition (Wiley, New York, 1989).
2. R. L. Byer, "Optical parametric oscillators," in *Quantum Electronics: A Treatise*, H. Rabin and C. L. Tang, ed. (Academic, New York, 1975), pp. 587-702.
3. J. A. Armstrong, N. Bloembergen, J. Ducuing, and P. S. Pershan, "Interactions between light waves in a nonlinear dielectric," *Phys. Rev.* **127**, 1918-1939 (1962).
4. M. Yamada, N. Nada, M. Saitoh, and K. Watanabe, "First-order quasi-phase matched LiNbO₃ waveguide periodically poled by applying an external field for efficient blue second-harmonic generation," *Appl. Phys. Lett.* **62**, 435-436 (1993).
5. M. M. Fejer, G. A. Magel, D. H. Jundt, and R. L. Byer, "Quasi-phase-matched second harmonic generation: tuning and tolerances," *IEEE J. Quantum Electron.* **28**, 2631-2654 (1992).
6. L. E. Myers, R. C. Eckardt, M. M. Fejer, R. L. Byer, W. R. Bosenberg, and J. W. Pierce, "Quasi-phaseshmatched optical parametric oscillators in bulk periodically poled LiNbO₃," *J. Opt. Soc. Am. B* **12**, 2102-2116 (1995).
7. V. Pruneri, J. Webjörn, P. S. J. Russell, and D. C. Hanna, "532 nm pumped optical parametric oscillator in bulk periodically poled lithium niobate," *Appl. Phys. Lett.* **67**, 2126-2128 (1995).
8. L. Goldberg, R. W. McElhanon, and W. K. Burns, "Blue light generation in bulk periodically poled LiNbO₃," *Electron. Lett.* **31**, 1576-1577 (1995).
9. L. E. Myers, G. D. Miller, R. C. Eckardt, M. M. Fejer, R. L. Byer, and W. R. Bosenberg, "Quasi-phaseshmatched 1.064-

- μm -pumped optical parametric oscillator in bulk periodically poled LiNbO_3 ," *Opt. Lett.* **20**, 52-54 (1995).
10. L. E. Myers, R. C. Eckardt, M. M. Fejer, R. L. Byer, and W. R. Bosenberg, "Multi-grating quasi-phases-matched optical parametric oscillator in periodically poled LiNbO_3 ," accepted for publication in *Opt. Lett.* (1996).
 11. W. R. Bosenberg, A. Drobshoff, and L. E. Myers, "High-power, high-repetition-rate optical parametric oscillators based on periodically poled LiNbO_3 ," in *Advanced Solid State Lasers*, 1996 Technical Digest Series, (Optical Society of America, Washington, DC, 1996), p. 68-70.
 12. L. E. Myers, R. C. Eckardt, M. M. Fejer, R. L. Byer, and J. W. Pierce, "CW diode-pumped optical parametric oscillator in bulk periodically poled LiNbO_3 ," *Electron. Lett.* **31**, 1869-1870 (1995).
 13. L. E. Myers, R. C. Eckardt, M. M. Fejer, R. L. Byer, and W. R. Bosenberg, "Progress in quasi-phases-matched optical parametric oscillators using periodically poled LiNbO_3 ," in *Nonlinear Frequency Conversion: Materials, Devices, and Applications*, Proc. SPIE 2700A, (1996).
 14. L. E. Myers, W. R. Bosenberg, W. M. Tulloch, M. A. Arbore, R. C. Eckardt, M. M. Fejer, and R. L. Byer, "CW singly-resonant optical parametric oscillators based on $1.064\text{-}\mu\text{m}$ -pumped periodically poled LiNbO_3 ," in *Advanced Solid State Lasers*, 1996 Technical Digest, (Optical Society of America, Washington, D.C., 1996), Paper PDP-5.
 15. W. R. Bosenberg, A. Drobshoff, J. I. Alexander, L. E. Myers, and R. L. Byer, "Continuous-wave singly-resonant optical parametric oscillator based on periodically-poled LiNbO_3 ," submitted to *Optics Letters* (1996).
 16. L. E. Myers, T. P. Grayson, W. R. Bosenberg, M. D. Nelson, V. Dominic, M. M. Fejer, and R. L. Byer, "Increasing the aperture of electric-field periodically-poled LiNbO_3 ," submitted to CLEO 1996.
 17. K. Mizuuchi and K. Yamamoto, "Harmonic blue light generation in bulk periodically poled LiTaO_3 ," *Appl. Phys. Lett.* **66**, 2943-2945 (1995).
 18. Q. Chen and W. P. Risk, "Periodic poling of KTiOPO_4 using an applied electric field," *Electron. Lett.* **30**, 1516-1517 (1994).
 19. H. Karlsson, F. Laurell, P. Henriksson, and G. Arvidsson, "Second-harmonic generation in periodically poled RbTiOAsO_4 ," in *Advanced Solid State Lasers*, 1996 Technical Digest, (Optical Society of America, Washington, D.C., 1996), Paper PDP-3.